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The Voice of the Marginal and the Poor Responsibility as the Basic Concept for Development Ethics in the Footsteps of Emmanuel Levinas

Roger Burggraeve SVD
Levinas Scholar, Catholic University,
Leuven, Belgium

Abstract: Taking on the suggestion of Ananta Kumar Giri that we should broaden and deepen development ethics with the thought of Emmanuel Levinas, the author tries to demonstrate how the ethical thought of Levinas about the other and the heteronomous responsibility for the other achieves this in an eminent manner. However, so that this responsibility would not lapse into the one-sidedness of old altruism, whereby the marginal and the poor would only be the objects of personal or organisational aid, he has developed out of Levinas' thought itself the idea of an emancipatory responsibility. The responsibility for the development of the marginal and the poor other essentially implies the idea of self-unfolding and thus of responsibility for oneself. But in order that this emancipatory responsibility in its turn would not turn into a new and disastrous one-sidedness, he has indicated with Levinas how the heteronomous responsibility for the other implies a responsibility for the responsibility of the other. Only by applying Levinas' idea of heteronomous responsibility to the marginal and the poor as well, is full justice done to the thesis that they are not only objects but likewise subjects of responsibility.

Keywords: Heteronomous responsibility, emancipatory responsibility, Levinas, vulnerability of the poor, development as responsibility.

The starting point for this reflection is the suggestion of Ananta Kumar Giri¹ that we should broaden and deepen development ethics with the thought of Emmanuel Levinas². For this purpose we begin with his famous idea of the face of the other as the source of responsibility. Insofar as the face of the other displays a radical alterity, it puts us on the track of the vulnerable other, which Levinas likewise calls “the poor, the widow, the orphan and the stranger”. This vulnerability, which manifests itself in an extreme manner in its mortality, reveals at the same time its mastership, which is from the very beginning an ethical mastership, meaning an appeal to responsibility. Not only will we lay bare the foundation of this responsibility but likewise make explicit its different major lines. Concretely speaking, we will demonstrate how the responsibility to which the vulnerable face appeals to us displays a multi-dimensional character. It indeed takes place as a responsibility for the responsibility of the other. And in its turn this implies a double line of responsibility. Firstly, there is an emancipatory aspect, namely a responsibility for the responsibility of the other – the poor, the widow, the orphan and the stranger – for oneself. And then there is likewise a strong ethically provocative aspect, namely the responsibility for the responsibility of the other for others.

1. The Mastership of the Marginal and the Poor

The core of Levinas’ thought consists in that he does not primarily link the vulnerability of the marginal and the poor with their factual condition of poverty or exclusion, but with the essential and radical alterity of the other, that is to say with the epiphany of the other as ‘other’ or as ‘face’. Hence we commence our search for the link between development ethics and Levinasian thought with a description of this alterity. The poor is not in the first place a poor person, but an other who as other directs oneself towards me.

The ‘I’, that by means of its capabilities and knowledge draws the world to itself, becomes as it were frightened by the epiphany of the other, precisely insofar as the other manifests itself as the *radically other*. The other presents itself to me as a ‘withdrawing’ and ‘transcending movement’, and this not only factually and temporarily but essentially and definitively. The other derives its

meaning not integrally and wholly from the world surrounding it, nor from evolution, history, a system of totality. The other surpasses all historical, sociological, psychological and cultural origin of meaning. The other presents itself as the unique one, that radically goes beyond all belonging to kind, race, family, tribe, ethnicity and people – which already implies a condemnation of all racism (VA 98). The other is already infinitely more than the images, photographs, representations, evocations and interpretations that I design or am able to design. Of course the other is visible; of course the other appears and evokes all sorts of impressions, images and representations, whereby the other is describable. Of course we can come to know much about the other on the basis of what the other allows to be seen somatically, psychologically and sociologically. But the other is always more than, and irreducible to, its photograph. This not only coincidentally or factually, but also in principle: the other can never be adequately represented and contained in one or the other image. I can never encase the other in, or equate the other with, its graphic form (EI 90-91/86-87). Even though the other has its own physiognomy and character, and thus a recognisable estimable feature, still its face precisely consists in breaking through and surpassing its own image and appearance time and again (AE 109/86). In so doing the other essentially escapes all typology, characterisation, diagnosis and classification – in short all attempts at knowing and understanding the other totally. The other makes all inquisitiveness ridiculous (TI 46/73-74). This implies that the other is not constituted by me as a supplement to my deficiency, and likewise not as my mirror image, alter-ego or ‘re-issue of myself’ (TA 75/83). In short, ‘the other is invisible’, as Levinas expresses it provocatively (TI 4/34). The face continually belies its own countenance, meaning to say its own visibility and describability. It is literally ‘*retraite*’ or ‘*anachore-sis*’, withdrawal. Its epiphany is always a breaking through, and a confounding of, this epiphany, whereby the other always remains enigmatic and thereby precisely intrudes as the irreducible one, the separate and different, the foreigner – in short, as the pre-eminently different or as radical alterity.

If we relate this to the marginal and the poor (dalits, proletarians, elderly, mentally disabled persons...), then this means that they

definitely have a biologically determined origin, but also that they transcend this origin infinitely. Poor persons always transcend their past and milieu. They never coincide with their appearance, family, psychology, sociology. They are always different from what their background appears to be or would lead us to suspect. They do not only remain a mystery factually but also principally. In this aspect poor persons are – no matter how visible or tangible – invisible. That means that they are irreducible to their tangible or descriptive characteristics. Sociology, psychology and other human sciences can most certainly make a contribution to ‘define’ the marginal and the poor, but they will never coincide with these descriptions. (Later on we will see how on the ethical level they *may* never be reduced to these descriptions). The poor as the radically other will always escape and show themselves different from the ‘foreseen’. Poor and marginal people will continue to surprise those who take care of them as the ones who are ultimately new and other!

This rather negative description of the alterity of the other in general, and of the poor in particular, however, has a clearly positive meaning. The basis for its in-visibility, un-knowability and unpredictability is indeed its ‘manifestati-on *kath’auto*’ (TI 37/65). The face breaks through its form in order to show itself out of itself. It is pure and simple ‘expression’ (TI 37/66). This self-expression occurs in a concrete manner in the word and glance of the face. The other is the one who looks at me straight in the eye and also directly addresses me: we stand ‘*face-to-face*’ with each other. Its glance and word make it present without any detours or intermediary stages. I need not reason out, starting from the fact that a glance or word comes toward me, in order to decide that someone lies behind this expression. The word and the glance of the other make it immediately, ineluctably and almost obtrusively present (LC 41/20). Moreover, the primary, most fundamental content or message of its self-expression is nothing else than the essential quality of the other, namely its absolute alterity and irreducibility. It is not *what* the face expresses that is of importance here, but *that* it expresses itself. The *fact* of its expression is the announcement of its very presence, of its appearance *as* other, whatever the content of its expression may be (TI 170/196).

In terms of the marginal and the poor this means that they can never be an object for the ones who take care of them or approach them. The marginal other will always be a face that speaks directly to them. The poor person is not an object, but a subject: someone who gazes at me, touches me and speaks to me with the authority of an other who comes to me. In this respect the poor person is always the one who literally comes to us: the poor comes from elsewhere, from itself – its alterity – as someone over whom we have no power (nor can we exercise power over it, as we will explain from an ethical position later). Maybe we can even say that the poor are ‘strong as death’, in the sense that through their gaze and (often wordless) word, they break into our existence and from within their alterity address us directly. The face of the poor is an ultimate heteronomous experience that we have not foreseen or could not predict. We therefore have no control over it. It is an experience that comes from an other who addresses us!

That is also why Levinas labels the expression of the other as *teaching*. This can in no possible way be reduced to one or other form of (Socratic) maieutics or midwifery that only draws out that which was already contained within. The expression of the face comes to me ‘from elsewhere’. It introduces more into myself than that which I already contain slumbering within me, namely, the real ‘message’ or ‘revelation’ of the presence of the other (TI 22/51): “the absolutely new is the other” (TI 194/219). The other manifests itself in its face as a strong alterity that from its height or loftiness directs itself immediately and authoritatively towards me (TI 175/200). In that sense Levinas can say that the other is my *master*: “The absolutely foreign alone can instruct us” (TI 46/73). By means of its very appearance, the other teaches me about its irreducible alterity without my having already contained this teaching within the depths of my being. In this regard, the fundamental teaching of the face is not without any imposition, not without any form of unassailability and a ‘self-sufficiency’ that is to be taken literally (a teaching that is sufficient in itself). Levinas even speaks of a “cold splendour” (TI 175/200). I am not able to let the teaching of the face bubble up from within me. I cannot foresee or predict the word of revelation of the face; I do not have it at hand in any way whatsoever. I am not the

one who designs, but the one who receives, who listens, and who, by means of listening, obeys (TI 41/69, 73/99).

Continuing in this line we can say that the marginal and the poor are elevated above us, not because they are more powerful, but because as irreducible others they are our master and teacher. Mostly we assume that the poor is lesser than us, precisely because he or she is small and vulnerable. But thanks to Levinas it becomes clear how we are in an asymmetrical relationship to the poor, in the sense that the poor is more than us, and we are less than the poor. We do not first teach and instruct the poor. First the poor has to speak to us and teach us. Every relationship of helping the poor has therefore to begin – every time again – with a form of humility and obedience to the poor as our teacher. We are talking here about a different life from what in Greek tradition is called self-knowledge: “know yourself” (“*gnothi seauton*”). In relationship to the marginal and the poor, as in every relationship to the other, I do not learn by descending into myself and discovering in my innermost being wisdom over all things, but by going out of myself and being open to the other as the other reveals him or herself to me. The relationship to the poor as the ultimate other is no autonomous or heteronomous happening that rests on the realisation of my not-knowing. In the relationship to the poor I am not the one who designs and determines, but the one who has to receive and accept what the other ‘teaches’ me. In this respect the alterity of the poor as the starting-point for my learning is not only exterior, but also anterior and superior. As the radical other the poor brings me towards laying down all pretensions and to approach her or him with a certain meekness, so that the face of the poor can in all liberty reveal its alterity to me, and this on the basis of the authority of this alterity.

In this way, Levinas turns around the usual, traditional vision of ‘caring for the marginal and the poor’. We are not in the first place the helping persons who pass on their insights, wisdom and convictions to the ‘receiving’ poor. It is the poor themselves who come first in assistance: the radical priority of the other. The face of the poor that speaks, is and becomes the first teacher of the ‘assistant’ person. As the radical other the poor establishes its mastership in all works of aid and assistance. In this way the face of the poor also

establishes the learning process of all kinds of (professional) people and organisations 'assisting' the poor, and this not just for once, but time and again.

2. The vulnerability of the marginal and the poor

With this turning around of mastership in 'assisting the marginal and the poor', we arrive at the ethical relationship to them. For the marginal and the poor do not only reveal their mastership in terms of their radical alterity, but through their alterity they appeal to us to recognise, respect and enhance their alterity. For the explication of the concrete content of this ethical relationship to the marginal and the poor, we return once again to the general insight of Levinas about the appeal to responsibility that comes to us in and through the face of the other.

Upon closer inspection, the mastership that ensues from the alterity of the face appears to be a very exceptional mastership. It is a mastership that rests on the vulnerability of the other whereby the mastership of the face becomes precisely an ethical mastership. The face, according to Levinas, is the remarkable fact that a being touches me not in the indicative but in the imperative (LC 44/21).

In order to understand how this functions, we must reflect more deeply on the phenomenology of the appearance, or rather the non-appearance, or epiphany, of the other. This we began above. The strong alterity of the face, insofar as it presents itself as its irreducibility to one or other 'countenance', photograph or representation, has a reverse side. It has an extreme vulnerability. Levinas calls this also "strangeness-destitution" (*l'étrangeté-misère*) (TI 47/75) or the 'nudity of the face' (EI 90/86). As a *countenance* the other is vulnerable. It can quite easily be reduced to its appearance, its family, its social position and environment, its accomplishments, its health and clinical picture. As 'in-visible', that is as being irreducible to its face, the other appears by not appearing. In short the other appears as the one who does not belong in my organised world – a world that I begin to organise precisely as 'my world' on the basis of my natural 'care for myself'. The face of the other eludes not only my foresight, literally my 'pro-vidence', it also falls outside of it. It finds itself literally in 'extra-territoriality' and 'u-topia' or

‘non-place’. Precisely for that reason is the face so vulnerable: “The transcendence of the face is at the same time its absence from this world into which it enters, the exiling of a being, his condition of being a stranger, destitute, or proletarian. The nakedness of the face extends into the nakedness of the body that is cold and that is ashamed of its nakedness. Existence *kath’auto* is, in the world, a destitution” (TI 47/75). “The face in its nakedness presents to me the destitution of the poor one and the stranger” (TI 188/213). The gravity of the other’s nakedness, destitution, or hunger, freezes all laughter. In its ‘height’ (*supra*), the other reveals also an extreme ‘humility’ – not as a virtue but as a condition (TI 174/200). And this condition of defencelessness is revealed most sharply in its mortality and suffering unto death (EN 166-167/124-125).

Levinas characterises this humility in an evocative manner by referring to the biblical terms “widow, orphan, stranger, poor” (TI 5078). However, we must be careful in the use of these terms. We could consider them as kinds or genres or groups of people with certain social characteristics, which distinguish them from others. But then we would indeed go beyond the true meaning of Levinas’ use of the terms. After all it is not on the basis of their qualities and thus not on the basis of their differences that these people are bearers of the radical, vulnerable alterity, which is Levinas’ main concern (VA 97). The question, however, is why does Levinas give a certain preference to these categories of people? Upon closer inspection, he is not so much interested in their qualities as in their essential vulnerability. By means of their social ‘condition’ they make visible and tangible the vulnerable nakedness of the other (although alterity itself is not visible and tangible). By means of their poverty, rejection and exile they stand closer to death than the others. Their mortality is more evident and notable. And that is precisely Levinas’ main concern when he concerns himself with the nakedness of the other. By using the metaphorical reference to the biblical groups of those ‘rejected’ and ‘naked’, Levinas wants to make clear that he is concerned with the vulnerability of the other, which manifests itself unto the body. It is about their ‘nearness to death’, their mortality, the coming closer to their suffering unto death... They ‘display’, or rather they evoke the essential vulnerability of every face, of every other. It involves the ‘precarious’ character of the other, namely its

assailable nakedness. Hence the use of qualifications like fragility, nudity, suffering, destitution, and especially ‘mortality’, to be understood as being under threat and exposure to death: “Exposure, pointblank, extradition of the beleaguered, the tracked down – tracked down before all tracking and all beating for game. Face as the very mortality of the other person” (EN 206/160). In this manner, a relationship arises between me and the other, which situates itself beyond all rhetoric: a relationship that qualifies all flattery, and even all poetry, about the other as ridiculous, or rather as repulsive, inappropriate and despicable.

This relationship, however, displays a remarkable character. Upon closer inspection it is precisely the appearance of the face as vulnerable (unto death) that invites me, as it were, to reduce the other to be a function of my own being. In this respect, Levinas takes the paradoxical position that the other presents itself to me as the ‘temptation to kill’ (EI 90/86). The nudity of the face is not only an ‘uncomfortable’ nudity – one that testifies to an essential destitution, as we said – it is also a ‘touchable’ nudity. By its destitution it invites me, as it were, to violence. By the condition of its humility the face seduces me to ‘integrate’ or to imprison the other in my self-interested effort of existing (AE 113-115/89-91). It is thanks to the essential vulnerability of the face that I, in my attempt at being that strives for happiness and meaning, am tempted to draw the other to myself and do it violence. This happens concretely by attempting to make the other subordinate to me, to take it in service, to consume and to use it in one way or another. For that purpose I often make use of the wealth and power that I have accumulated for myself out of my expansionistic vitalism. I can use, or rather abuse, all possible means in order to reduce the other to myself, to blackmail, to intimidate or to bribe it, in short to subjugate it – without giving the direct impression of a brutal tyranny or slavery. In its extreme form, this will to power flows from the denial of the other. Of this, murder as the total negation or annihilation of the other, is the physical incarnation (TI 172/198).

What can we deduce from this position of the ‘attraction to kill’ with respect to the ethical relationship to the poor? It leads us to recognise that violence in relationships between people, is a realistic

possibility and may not be seen as an exception related to perverse and sadistic persons. Precisely on the basis of the nakedness and vulnerability of the poor the possibility for violence is real. Violence displays many faces. The extreme cases of the physical violence of murder and all kinds of abuse are not alone. There is also hate, tyranny, intimidation, blackmail, bullying and the refusal to give recognition, or exclusion and neglect. There is subjection, manipulation, oppression and slavery. Violence includes all forms of both direct and more subtle forms of indifference. There is the violence that flows from approaching the poor on the basis of perception and knowledge. It is precisely in the daily perception and exploration of the poor that the greatest risk for violence lies, in the sense that it does not take much to reduce the poor to its appearance, that means to its situation and reality of destitution.

3. The Heteronomous Responsibility for the Other Begins as a Prohibition

In this very temptation to kill lies the ethical significance of the face. At the moment in which I am tempted to reduce the other to a means of my own existence, I simultaneously realise that that which can be, actually must not be. This is the core of the fundamental ethical experience beginning from the face of the poor as the other (LC 44/21-22). In my self-sufficient effort at existing, which on the ground of perception and representation aims to become the expression and realisation of individual freedom, I am not merely limited from the outside but in my deepest being. I am – in the very principle of my freedom – shaken and called into question (EI 129/120). In the face I discover myself as the potential murderer of the other. In this sense, through the destitution of the other I stumble once again upon its substantial strength. I come up against a radical resistance against my egocentric, reducing avarice. The face appears as the *opposite*: it takes up a position *before* me as a radical and immediate ‘stop’ or *no*, as an absolute opposition to all my capabilities (TI 173-174/198-199). The *logos* of this ‘no’, the first wordless word that ensues from the face of the other, namely the poor, is then also a prohibition: ‘You shall not kill’ (EN 48/30). You shall not make the other into a means for yourself. Moreover, this

resistance against the denial and instrumental reduction of the other is in no way coincidental or accidental. Indeed, it does not rest on a free decision of the other but on its essential alterity itself, which as vulnerability is at the same time an unparalleled protest against every grasp of this vulnerability by the 'I' and its attempt at being that is concerned for itself (HS 141/93-94).

From all this appears something very paradoxical. The ethical relationship with the other, the poor as the other, begins as a shock experience, namely, the possibility *and* the prohibition to do violence to the other in any way whatsoever. This implies that the ethical relationship with the poor does not begin with a positive commandment that determines what I *must* do, but rather with a negative intervention, a prohibition that questions the straightforward-without-beating-about-the-bush movement of the attempt at being. At the same time, it concerns an external law, which does not come up from within the dynamism of the 'living being' itself. The fundamental ethical sensitivity that is aroused by the external prohibition against violence is a remarkable form of fear. Not the fear or concern for oneself, but the fear of being after the blood of the other. Levinas in this regard also speaks of the scruple. Literally, the word 'scruple' means a 'pebble in one's shoe'. It becomes impossible to stand still, and instead moves or incites one to take another step. A scruple, therefore, is a disquiet that works its way through the soul obstructively. The scruple can likewise be understood as a form of shame and discomfort: I am apprehensive about the other, namely the poor, as to its irreducible being-other, whereby it is surrendered to me to seize and to do violence, to violate, to pest, to maltreat, to abuse, to deny or to destroy, in short to 'kill' in one way or the other and to do it injustice (DVI 254/169). We can then label this first ethical movement before the vulnerable other as an "apparently negative movement of restraint" (NLT 96/126). Confronted with the principal assailability *and* vulnerability of the other, I am called to restrain myself and to pull back – in other words, to *not* do something. The ethics towards the poor as the radical other begins as the paradox of 'restraint', curtailment or 'self-contraction' in the midst of the unabashed and energetic way with which our caring for ourselves rushes forward without looking right or left, without seeing the 'corpses' it leaves aside. Or to put it in different

terms, the ethical relationship towards the other begins as a hesitation, a shame over oneself, as a movement of withdrawal and self-questioning. I may feel inclined to ask myself questions along the lines of: “Am I perhaps too ‘vehement’, too self-assured and insouciant, only concerned about my own happiness, future and meaning? Do I perhaps ‘kill’ (i.e. not allow space for others to be) simply by being myself?” The appearance of the poor as the other touches and traumatises me to the very core of my heart, so much so that I am “suffering in my skin” (AE 66/51).

All of this implies that the ethical responsibility for the marginal and the poor has to begin with the respect for the commandment: ‘You shall not kill’. No form of violence towards poor people is acceptable, whether in the context of daily life, economics, or society. The demand for strict non-violence is the primary ethical task of people working with the poor. It is such a fundamental ethical duty, that it precedes all other ethical approaches to the poor. Its fundamental character is simultaneously utterly paradoxical. By not killing or by not using any form of violence one has in effect not yet done anything. Through obedience to the commandment not to kill the preconditions are created in which things still need to be done.

The fact in itself that we have in our societies the prohibition ‘You shall not kill’, ‘You shall not commit violence towards the marginal and the poor’, indicates not only the unacceptability of this violence, but also the fact that violence towards the marginal and poor other is not that strange or exceptional. There would not be an ethical prohibition as expression of practical ethical wisdom if there had been no violence towards people in general, and against the marginal and the poor in particular. Human civilisation exists precisely in recognising the potential of factual violence towards the poor (and all vulnerable others) so that something can be done about it, through sanctioning, for example, where the prohibition of violence is not respected.

By means of the prohibition and the ethical scruple or restraint awakened in me, the radical ethical asymmetry or ‘non-reciprocity’ between me and the other, namely the poor, becomes visible. In contrast to Buber’s idea of the reciprocity between ‘I’ and ‘Thou’, Levinas speaks about “the ‘curvature’ of the intersubjective space”

(TI 267/291). Through the prohibition the 'I' and the other or the poor are not only radically separated from each other, they are also distinct. And, note well, this discrepancy does not depend on their respectively distinct characteristics or on their coincidentally unequal psychological dispositions and moods during the encounter (TI 190/215). It lies in the 'I-other-conjunction' itself: through its demanding, prohibiting, character the face of the vulnerable other stands above me as an *authority* that comes upon me from its ethical 'height' making demands and claims. We can label this as the 'sacred' and 'divine' character of the face of the poor. As such the marginal as the other then is not my equal, but my *superior*: not only my master who reveals something radically new, as we have seen above, but also my 'lord' who as a 'Thou' commands me unconditionally from its eminently ethical height (TI 74-75/100-101). That is precisely the paradox of the epiphany of the face of the poor: as the factual inferior, the poor as the radical other is ethically my superior. In this way it refers to the sublime awe and majesty of God. Thus the mastership of the marginal and the poor as the other sketched above, is reinforced, or, rather, ethically qualified.

4. The Emancipatory Dimension of Heteronomous Responsibility

Only through obedience to the prohibition of violence is space created for a positive filling in of a respectful responsibility that allows the poor and the marginal to unfold and raise their voice: the voice of the irreducible, exalted other. This responsibility is more than not killing or not making use of any violence. It is an attitude of acknowledgement and respect for the being-other of the poor. And it does not stop at this. It unfolds itself even further. It must be *more* than the 'appreciative respect'. It must develop into a responsibility 'in deeds and actions', meaning to say into a responsibility that expresses itself in concrete deeds of care that are directed towards the well-being of the other, namely the poor. Responsibility is thus neither the sentimentalism nor the naïve romanticism of being moved by the miserable and marginalised poor. Its affectiveness must turn into effectiveness, its dedication to the other into 'works' of care for the other (HAH 40-44/90-93). Without incarnation the responsibility

for the other is hollow and empty. Stronger still, it is a lie and denial of oneself. How can one be concerned for the other if one performs no concrete deeds as the expression of this concern? Or to put it in a rabbinical way: it is not enough to love the other with our heart and soul, when we do not also love the other with our money, and even more so, with our hospitality. It is so that when you let the naked into your house he makes the floor mat dirty. In short, our yes-word must become flesh – in and through our body – and that in economic-earthly, appropriate forms (AS 81).

Applied to the responsibility for the marginal and the poor, this means that one must take up concrete care for the ‘being’ of the other, in this case the poor and excluded other, meaning to say for their life and ‘well-being’ (to be understood literally as the tangible unfolding of being). As a bodily other, the poor is in the first place a needy and finite and thus vulnerable creature, who needs others for its survival and good life. This flows forth directly from one’s essential nakedness and vulnerability, that expresses itself in an extreme manner in one’s mortality, as was sketched above. Or to put differently still: the essential alterity of the other takes place and reveals itself in the other’s factual shortcomings and injuries of one’s ‘conatus essendi’. “The other’s hunger – be it of the flesh or of bread – is sacred; there is no bad materialism other than our own” (DL 12/XIV). It would be a hypocritical form of spiritualism if in the responsibility for others, namely the poor, one would not take up any care for their nourishment and clothing, their protection against heat and cold, disease and accidents, “as if the entire spirituality on earth did not reside in the act of nourishing” (DL 12). The unrelenting suffering, that incarnates in a concrete way the essential nakedness of the poor and the marginal other, requires what Levinas calls “the severe seriousness of goodness” whereby the fate of the misery that the other meets loses its inhuman character (TI 175/200). Hence Levinas cites in this context the ‘hard’ words of the Jewish Rabbi Jochanan: “To leave men without food is a fault that no circumstance attenuates” (TI 175/201). Towards the hunger of people, our responsibility is unrelenting! In this regard, the ‘rich’ are objectively and fully responsible for the elimination of poverty. The ethics of heteronomous responsibility of the one for the other has a very ‘worry-some’ and disturbing meaning, namely to confront

the 'well-to-do' with the vulnerable, marginal and poor others. To relieve the others with food and drink is not a question of non-committal or gratuitous charity, meaning to say of good intentions and good resolutions, but an inescapable duty of justice. And this duty to responsibility goes so far, says Levinas, that when giving food and drink no longer helps, one still does not leave the other to its fate in its irreversible suffering and dying. Herein lies the most tangible and ultimate criterion of the responsibility for the other, and thus of human civilisation: "facing the face, in its mortality" (EN 206/160). This even leads Levinas to formulate a new categorical imperative: "You shall not let the other alone, be it in the face of the inexorable" (EI 128/119).

There is more, however, than this incarnation of the responsible care for every other, in particular the marginal and poor other. Not only do we have to answer for their bodily being and well-being, but also for the unfolding of their 'attempt at being' into an independent and free existence. Oftentimes, the poor – especially when the excluded are concerned – avail of only a very limited freedom, which they only are able to receive and develop thanks to the responsibility of others in society. In that sense, the promotion of the poor into independent and active persons does not contradict the heteronomous responsibility for the other; the responsibility for the self-unfolding of the other flows forth directly from heteronomous responsibility. The responsibility by and for the other sees to it that 'mastership', which was discussed above in our description of the radical alterity of the face of the poor, acquires its true ethical form. By means of our responsibility for the naked and sidetracked poor, we effectively make possible their ethical mastership. The responsibility for the poor after all implies essentially the care for their becoming independent and mature. Stronger still, without the asymmetrically responsible care by-and-for-the-other, the marginal and the poor cannot even grow into active, able persons. The heteronomous responsibility for the poor as the radical other is the condition of possibility for the development of that poor other into a subject responsible-for-oneself. According to Levinas this is precisely the paradox of the heteronomous responsibility for the poor: it is a strongly concrete responsibility, in the sense that it is geared towards the being and self-development of the other. To take heteronomous

responsibility for the poor concretely means to create space and possibilities for the growth of the poor to independence and responsibility for itself. This means anything but a negative or suspicious approach to the weak and the poor in their attempts to take their own responsibility. If the poor and marginal person is not an object, but an other, a subject, then we have to treat the poor as a full human person. When necessary, we will make critical remarks, so that poor and marginalised people can adjust their active responsibility and develop it better.

Furthermore, the heteronomous responsibility for the poor also means that one should pay attention to the many hurts that alienate marginalised persons from themselves so that, through caring closeness, they can heal sufficiently from these wounds. In this way a poor person can become the best possible responsible 'I': a responsible self that not only asserts itself, but also acts and speaks from within itself. In this sense, we are responsible for the responsibility poor and marginal people should have for themselves. With Levinas we can here even go further and speak of a substitute responsibility. During the decisive moments of growth and development, and from within our own task of responsibility, we take the lack of responsibility of the vulnerable, the weak and the poor unto ourselves. In this way, too, responsible ones for others recognise and promote the uniqueness of the poor and marginal other. We can call all of this the emancipatory aspect of each and every responsibility by and for the poor other: the possibility to enable and promote the responsibility of the poor for and by itself and through which it becomes an active responsible agent. In this manner, the marginal and poor others are no longer reduced to 'target groups' and 'objects', meaning to say to 'beneficiaries of development', but are transformed into 'subjects' and agents of their own development. The marginal and the poor are not only 'recipients' of development aid; they are also responsible for their own development.

5. Responsible for the Responsibility of the Marginal and the Poor for Others

We do wish to go even one step beyond Levinas' philosophical vision of heteronomous responsibility, though we remain indebted

to him for our inspiration. We wish to turn around the asymmetrical responsibility by and for the other and look at it from the perspective of the responsibility of the marginal and the poor for others. We call this a chiasmic responsibility, in the sense that we are speaking of two types of responsibility that cross one another. Our responsibility for others, namely for the marginal and the poor, is only integral if it grows into the responsibility for the responsibility of poor people, not only for themselves (cf. *supra*) but also, and especially for, others. If we then only apply the idea of responsibility for the other to the people taking care of the poor and the marginal, our analysis is lacking. It will give rise to a partiality that leads to disastrous results.

It is very well possible that people caring for the marginal and the poor, with all their commitment and energy, end up in an egocentric result with the ones they take care of. The caring responsibility for the other can be very altruistic and unselfish, but this can imply that the other – the object of this care – is promoted into a self-complacent life, wherein only the care for oneself is important. To put it in paradoxical terms, the altruism of the one can lead directly to a promotion of the egotism of the other. We should not be blind to the fact that hunger, poverty and exclusion, in short all sorts of forms of deprivation and need, drive people to a hard and unrelenting ‘struggle for life’. Poverty brings back the person to one’s ‘natural existence’, in the sense that by means of one’s fragile and finite being one is incited in ‘life and limb’ to be concerned about one’s own being. The more acute the needs, even more the needy person becomes an ‘impassioned’ person, meaning to say a creature that is concerned for its own being and sees everything and everyone in the light of the satisfaction of its own needs. With Levinas we can label this as an unavoidable, natural selfishness, in the sense that the poor – precisely as poor – approach everything and everyone out of themselves and their own survival. In this regard poverty manifests itself as ‘animal existence’. This ‘banal’ approach of poverty, that throws back the needy to the (at times fanatic) care for their own being, implies a direct critique on the idea of ‘self-actualisation’, which in Western late-modern thought was developed by a number of authors (Rogers, Maslow, ...). The link between poverty and the egocentric struggle for life unmasks the thought on self-unfolding as naïve, stronger still as typically Western, in the sense

that it expresses *and* justifies the Western context of wealth and welfare. That is why the manner in which Levinas speaks about the natural striving of humans to be ('conatus essendi') seems more honest and more realistic than the 'romantic' discourse about an 'aesthetics of Self-Cultivation' (Foucault).³ Therefore, the emancipatory promotion of the poor, sketched above, into a free self-determining and creative agent should never have the final word. The heteronomous responsibility by and for the other must go further. It must not only be an expression of the self-transcendence in the caring person, but also in the one taken care for, namely the poor. In society we are responsible for the responsibility of the marginal and the poor, in the sense that they must invite and provoke them into responsibility for others, and not only into responsibility for themselves. The one being responsible for the other is faced with the task to take up in such a manner its heteronomous responsibility for the other so that the other is guided and stimulated likewise to acknowledge, to take up and to develop its heteronomous responsibility by and for the other. When this does not take place, heteronomous responsibility contradicts itself. It even destroys its own dynamism and meaning: out of an extreme attention to the one affirmed as the radical other, that other is then brought to a place in a central position, at the cost of others.

This also concretely implies that in society the marginal and the poor are confronted with a number of boundary rules. Of these, 'You shall not kill' is the most fundamental. It is the minimal but strictly necessary condition for humane social life and for the creative development of the responsibility for the other, to which the poor must precisely be appealed. In a humane society we have the ethical mission to initiate and to introduce everyone, and therefore also the marginal and the poor, into the major importance of this prohibition, and also into a fundamental respect for it. All that was said above about the prohibition to violence can be applied without hesitation to the marginal and the poor as active agents. To put it in the words of Levinas: "The *vital* life, the natural life, perhaps begins in a naiveté and in repugnancies agreeing with ethics; it ends in compliance with loveless debauchery and looting erected into a social condition, into exploitation. *Human* life begins where this vitality, innocent in appearance, but virtually destructive, is mastered by interdictions.

Does not authentic civilization, whatever be the biological echoes or the political defects it brings to pass, consist in holding back the breath of naive life and thus awakening 'for posterity and to the end of all generations'?" (NLT 25-26/61-62). All persons, without exception, must be guided in order to transcend their natural, vitalistic existence towards the other and for the sake of the other: a limitation through which life awakens from its somnambulant spontaneity, sobers up from its nature, and interrupts its centripetal movement, to open itself to the otherness of the other (NLT 23/60). When this is neither the goal nor the result of interpersonal and social responsibility, then we fail in our task. Taking of the marginal and the poor even ends up in an anti-society, in spite of all the possible means and forms whereby the marginal and the poor are made capable of leading a happy and prosperous life as active agents. Then they have not yet grown beyond the level of their natural urge-to-be and urge-to-live into the level of humane civilisation. In short, a humane, ethically qualified society consists in this that we appeal to the responsibility of the marginal and the poor, not only for the cooperation in the unfolding and possible healing of their own freedom and attempt at being, but also, and especially, in order to take upon themselves, and creatively substantiate, the responsibility for other.

Finally, if the idea of the marginal and the poor as responsible and active agents is disconnected from the concept of the heteronomous responsibility for others but itself, it will flow into all sorts of conflict, aggression, threats and violence. If the free exercise of independence is left to its own, and so can not be inspired from within by the responsibility for the other, it easily becomes a insolent demand for freedom that thrashes about wildly and actively terrorises others. Only an inspired freedom, that is, a freedom that allows itself to be inspired by the other, is able to transcend self-centredness and to enter into true humane relationships with others. This is also the case for the marginal and the poor in all their interpersonal and social relationships.⁴

Conclusion

To re-imagine and reinvent development as a transformative practice, Giri proposes to “reconstitute development as responsibility, which can provide a self-critical and transformative supplement to the contemporary definitions of development as freedom”.⁵ We have attempted to demonstrate how the ethical thought of Levinas about the other and the heteronomous responsibility for the other, achieves this in an eminent manner. However, so that this responsibility would not lapse into the one-sidedness of the old altruism, whereby the marginal and the poor would only be the objects of personal or organisational aid, we have developed out of Levinas’ thought itself the idea of an emancipatory responsibility. The responsibility for the development of the marginal and the poor other essentially implies the idea of self-unfolding and thus of responsibility for oneself. But in order that this emancipatory responsibility in its turn would not turn into a new and disastrous one-sidedness, we have indicated with Levinas how the heteronomous responsibility for the other implies a responsibility for the responsibility of the other. Only by applying Levinas’ idea of heteronomous responsibility to the marginal and the poor as well, is full justice done to the thesis that they are not only objects but likewise subjects of responsibility.

Notes

1. See among others his study “Rethinking the Imperative of Responsibility: Development Ethics, Aesthetics, and the Challenge of Poverty,” in A.K. GIRI, *New Horizons of Social Theory. Conversations, Transformations and Beyond*, Jaipur/New Dehli/Bangalore/Mumbai/Hydrabad, Rawat Publications, 2006, p. 199-221, esp. pp. 207-211.
2. The cited studies of Levinas are listed below in alphabetical order. Citations in our text are indicated with an abbreviation of the original French edition, along with the cited page or pages. The cited page from the available English translation is indicated after the forward slash (/). Abbreviations used:

AE: *Autrement qu’être ou au-delà de l’essence*, La Haye, Nijhoff, 1974.
[English translation (ET): *Otherwise than Being or Beyond Essence*,

translated by A. Lingis, The Hague/Boston/London, Nijhoff (Kluwer), 1981.];

AS: *Autrement que savoir* (Interventions in the discussions and Débat général), Paris, Osiris, 1988;

CPP: *Collected Philosophical Papers*, translated by A. Lingis. Dordrecht/Boston/Lancaster, Kluwer/Nijhoff, 1987;

DL: *Difficile Liberté ; Essais sur le Judaïsme*, Paris, Albin Michel, 1976 (2nd ed.).

ET: *Difficult Freedom. Essays on Judaism*, translated by S. Hand. Baltimore, The John Hopkins University Press, 1990.];

DVI: *De Dieu qui vient à l'idée*, Paris, Vrin, 1982. [ET: *Of God Who Comes to Mind*, translated by B. Bergo, Stanford, University Press, 1998;

EI: *Éthique et Infini. Dialogues avec Philippe Nemo*, Paris, Fayard & France Culture, 1982. [ET: *Ethics and Infinity. Conversations with Philippe Nemo*, translated by R.A. Cohen, Pittsburgh, Duquesne University Press, 1985.];

EN: *Entre nous. Essais sur le penser-à-l'autre*, Paris, Grasset 1991. [ET: *Entre nous. Thinking-of-the-Other*, translated by M.B. Smith and B. Harshav, London/New York, Continuum, 2006];

HAH: *Humanisme de l'autre homme*, Montpellier, Fata Morgana, 1972. [ET: The three essays are taken up in CPP, respectively "Meaningful Sense" at pp. 75-107, "Humanism and Anarchy" at pp. 127-139, and "No identity" at pp. 141-151.];

HS: *Hors sujet*, Montpellier, Fata Morgana, 1987. [ET: *Outside the Subject*, translated by M.B. Smith, London, Athlone, 1993.];

LC: "Liberté et commandement" (suivi de "Transcendance et hauteur"), Montpellier, Fata Morgana, 1994. [ET: "Freedom and Command," in CPP, pp. 15-45.];

NLT: *Nouvelles lectures talmudiques*, Paris, Minuit, 1996. [ET: *New Talmudic Readings*, translated by R.A. Cohen, Pittsburgh, Duquesne University Press, 2000.];

TA: *Le temps et l'autre*, Montpellier, Fata Morgana, 1979 (2nd ed.). [ET: *Time and the Other*, translated by R.A. Cohen, Pittsburgh, Duquesne University Press, 1987.];

TI: *Totalité et Infini. Essai sur l'extériorité*, La Haye, Nijhoff, 1961. [ET: *Totality and Infinity An Essay on Exteriority*, translated by A. Lingis, The Hague/Boston/London, Nijhoff, 1979.];

- VA: "La vocation de l'autre" (interview with E. Hirsch), in: E. HIRSCH, *Racismes. L'autre et son visage*, Paris, Cerf, 1988, p. 89-102.
3. A.K. GIRI, Art. Cit., pp. 207-208.
 4. This requires the further elaboration of the social, economic and political dimension of the Levinasian concept of the heteronomous responsibility by and for the other. For that purpose we refer to our studies: 'The Other in Me: Interpersonal and Social Responsibility in Emmanuel Levinas', in *Revista Portuguesa de Filosofia*, 62(2006), pp. 631-649; *The Wisdom of Love in the Service of Love. Emmanuel Levinas on Justice, Peace, and Human Rights*, Milwaukee, Marquette University Press, 2002, 2003 (2nd ed.), 213 p.
 5. A.K. GIRI, Art. cit., p. 208.